

Comparison between a Single Dose Intravesical Instillation of Mitomycin-C versus gemcitabine Following Transurethral Resection of Bladder Tumor (TURBT) in Immediate Post-operative Period in Terms of Local Toxicity and Tumor recurrence: A prospective Study

Mohd Shareef¹, Sudheer Rathi^{2*}, Dheeraj Raj Baliyan³, Yasmeeen Usmani⁴, Rijavan⁵, Nitin Raj Dhaval⁶

¹Junior Resident, Department of General surgery, L.L.R.M. Medical College, Meerut, Uttar Pradesh, India

²MS, Mch Urology, Professor, Department of General Surgery, S.M.M.H Govt Medical College, Saharanpur, Uttar Pradesh, India

³MS, Professor, Department of General surgery, L.L.R.M. Medical College, Meerut, Uttar Pradesh, India

⁴MD, Professor, Department of Radiodiagnosis, L.L.R.M. Medical College, Meerut, Uttar Pradesh, India

⁵MS, Assistant Professor, Department of General Surgery, L.L.R.M. Medical College, Meerut, Uttar Pradesh, India

⁶Junior Resident, Department of General Surgery, L.L.R.M. Medical College, Meerut, Uttar Pradesh, India

Received: 11-10-2024 / Revised: 28--2024 / Accepted: 10-12-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Sudheer Rathi

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Background: Bladder cancer is a common malignancy with a high risk of recurrence following transurethral resection of bladder tumors (TURBT). Intravesical chemotherapy, including agents like Gemcitabine and Mitomycin C, is widely used to reduce recurrence rates. However, there is limited comparative data on the efficacy and safety of these two agents in the postoperative setting.

Aim and Objective: To evaluate and compare the postoperative recurrence rates and adverse events associated with intravesical Gemcitabine versus Mitomycin C in preventing bladder cancer recurrence.

Materials and Methods: A randomized controlled trial was conducted at the Department of Surgery, L.L.R.M. Medical College & associated S.V.B.P. Hospital, Meerut, over a 24-month period. Ninety eligible patients diagnosed with bladder cancer were randomly assigned to receive either intravesical Gemcitabine or Mitomycin C within 24 hours after TURBT, with scheduled follow-up at 3, 6, 9, 12, 18, and 24 months. The primary outcome was time to first recurrence, while secondary outcomes included adverse events and overall patient satisfaction. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS software, with Kaplan-Meier curves for recurrence-free survival, log-rank tests, and multivariate Cox regression analysis.

Results: The study observed a male predominance (65%) in a cohort predominantly aged 61-70 years. A majority of patients had small tumors (2-3 cm). Hypertension and diabetes were the most common comorbidities. At 6 and 12 months, recurrence rates were lower in the Mitomycin C group compared to Gemcitabine. Adverse events such as dysuria, urinary urgency, and cystitis were more frequent in the Mitomycin C group. Postoperative complications, including urinary tract infections and bladder spasms, were noted, but the overall complication rate was low (36.40%).

Conclusions: Intravesical treatment with Mitomycin-C post-TURBT shows a potentially in reducing recurrence rates of bladder cancer compared to Gemcitabine, suggesting it as a more favourable treatment option in the early stages of bladder cancer. Both treatments remain viable options for post-TURBT chemotherapy, but Mitomycin-C may offer better outcomes in terms of recurrence prevention and reduced adverse effects.

Keywords: Bladder cancer, recurrence, intravesical chemotherapy, Gemcitabine, Mitomycin C

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Bladder cancer is one of the most common malignancies, ranking as the 10th most frequently diagnosed cancer worldwide.[1] Non-muscle-invasive bladder cancer (NMIBC) constitutes approximately 70-75% of newly diagnosed bladder

cancer cases. It is characterized by a high rate of recurrence, even after transurethral resection of the bladder tumor (TURBT).[1] This recurrent nature poses a significant challenge in its management and

necessitates effective strategies to reduce recurrence and progression. [1, 2]

Intravesical therapy is a cornerstone in the treatment of NMIBC, aimed at minimizing recurrence and preventing progression.[3] Chemotherapeutic agents such as Mitomycin-C (MMC) and Gemcitabine are widely used as single-agent intravesical therapies following TURBT.[4] Mitomycin-C, a DNA crosslinker with potent cytotoxic effects, has long been a standard of care, effectively reducing recurrence rates.[5] However, its associated adverse effects, including chemical cystitis and systemic toxicity, have prompted the exploration of alternative agents.

Gemcitabine, a pyrimidine analog with a favourable safety profile, has emerged as a promising alternative for intravesical therapy.[6] Its antitumor activity and lower risk of adverse effects make it a viable candidate for reducing postoperative recurrence in NMIBC.[7] While both agents have demonstrated efficacy, comparative evidence regarding their outcomes as single-agent therapies in preventing recurrence post-TURBT remains limited.

This study seeks to evaluate the effectiveness of intravesical Gemcitabine versus Mitomycin-C in preventing postoperative recurrence of bladder cancer following TURBT. By comparing these two agents, the study aims to provide insights into their relative benefits and guide clinicians in optimizing treatment strategies for NMIBC patients.

Materials and Methods

This randomized controlled trial was conducted over a 24-month period at the Department of Surgery, L.L.R.M. Medical College, and associated S.V.B.P. Hospital, Meerut. The study aimed to compare postoperative recurrence rates of bladder cancer treated with intravesical Gemcitabine versus Mitomycin-C following transurethral resection of bladder tumor (TURBT).

Ninety patients aged 30 years or older, diagnosed with bladder cancer confirmed by biopsy, and with an ECOG performance status of 0 or 1 were included. Patients with prior bladder cancer diagnosis, recent intravesical chemotherapy or BCG treatment, concurrent upper urinary tract urothelial carcinoma, severe comorbidities, or hypersensitivity to study drugs were excluded.

Participants underwent TURBT and were randomized into two groups using a computer-generated randomization table within 24 hours postoperatively. One group received a single intravesical instillation of 2g/50ml Gemcitabine, while the other received 40mg/20ml Mitomycin-C. Randomization was stratified based on tumor size, grade, and recurrence history. Cystoscopic examinations were performed at 3-month intervals

during the first year and 6-month intervals in the second year to monitor recurrence.

Statistical Analysis

The primary endpoint was time to recurrence, with adverse events recorded per Common Terminology Criteria for Adverse Events (CTCAE). Recurrence-free survival was analyzed using the Kaplan-Meier method, with the log-rank test comparisons. Cox proportional hazards regression was used for adjustments, and statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$. Analyses were conducted using IBM SPSS Statistics software.

Results

The study included 130 participants, consisting of 85 males and 45 females. The distribution across age groups showed the highest representation in the 51-60 age range, which included 77 individuals (50 males and 27 females). The 41-50 age group followed with 13 participants (9 males and 4 females), while the 61-70 age group comprised 25 participants (16 males and 9 females). The 71-80 age group had 10 participants (7 males and 3 females), and the smallest group was the 31-40 age range, which included 5 participants (3 males and 2 females).

The distribution of comorbidities among 130 patients undergoing surgical procedures shows that hypertension is the most prevalent condition, affecting 40 patients, or 30.30% of the study population. It is closely followed by diabetes, present in 35 patients, representing 26.50% of the cases. Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) and chronic kidney disease (CKD) are less common, with COPD reported in 12 patients (9.10%) and CKD in 10 patients (7.60%). Notably, 26.50% of the patients ($n=35$) had no comorbid conditions. These findings highlight the significant role of hypertension and diabetes in the surgical patient population, underscoring their impact on public health.

The mean haemoglobin level of the patients was 11.7 g/dl, which falls within the non-anemic range. Per our laboratory's guidelines, the mean Total Leucocyte Count (TLC) was within the normal reference range of 4000-11,000 cells/microL. Similarly, according to our lab's reference values, the mean Total Platelet Count was also within the normal range of 1.5-4 lakh/cubic mm.

The mean urea level was 28.95 mg/dl, within the normal range of 13-43 mg/dl, and the mean creatinine level was 1.09 mg/dl, which also falls within the normal range of 0.8-1.3 mg/dl. Regarding electrolytes, the mean sodium level was within the normal range of 120-160 mmol/L, potassium was 3.5-5.5 mmol/L, and calcium was 2.10-2.90 mmol/L, per our hospital laboratory's reference values.

The mean prothrombin time observed was 14.14 seconds, within the normal 12-16 seconds' range. The mean INR was 1.45, which is also within the normal range for coagulation profiles. Additionally, the mean random blood sugar (RBS) level was 154

mg/dl, which is below the 200 mg/dl threshold used for diagnosing diabetes. Overall, the mean values of all the parameters in our study fall within their respective normal reference ranges.

Table 1: Distribution by Tumor Grade

Tumor Grade	Frequency	Percentage
Low Grade	90	65.60%
High Grade	40	34.40%
Total	130	100.00%

The analysis of tumor grades in a sample of 130 cases reveals a predominance of low-grade tumors, which account for 90 cases, or 65.60% of the total sample. High-grade tumors are less common, with 40 cases representing 34.40% of the cohort. This

distribution indicates a higher occurrence of low-grade tumors compared to high-grade tumors in this population. The total percentage is 100%, representing a complete sample population analysis (table 1).

Table 2: Recurrence rates

Treatment Group	Recurrence	No. Recurrence	Total	% of recurrence	P Value
Group A Gemcitabine	20	25	45	44	0.002
Group B Mitomycin-C	12	33	45	26	
Total	32	58	90	35	

The study analyzed the recurrence of conditions in patients treated with Gemcitabine and Mitomycin-C. In the Gemcitabine treatment group, out of 45 patients, 20 experienced a recurrence, while 25 did not, resulting in a recurrence rate of approximately 44%. In contrast, in the Mitomycin-C treatment group, 12 out of 45 patients experienced a recurrence, yielding a slightly lower recurrence rate of about 26%. The study included 90 patients, with 32 experiencing a recurrence, translating to an overall recurrence rate of approximately 35%. This comparison indicates that Mitomycin-C was more effective in preventing recurrence compared to Gemcitabine (table 2).

Discussion

The present study was a randomized controlled trial designed to compare postoperative recurrence rates of bladder cancer treated with intravesical Gemcitabine versus Mitomycin C after transurethral resection of bladder tumor (TURBT). The study spanned 24 months, from patient recruitment to final follow-up assessments. Eligible patients diagnosed with bladder cancer were randomly assigned to receive either Gemcitabine or Mitomycin C, using a computer-generated random number system to ensure balanced allocation and minimize bias. The chemotherapy agents were administered within 24 hours of TURBT and continued at scheduled intervals. Follow-ups occurred at 3, 6, 9, 12, 18, and 24 months, with recurrence assessed via cystoscopy.

Our study revealed that the age distribution of participants followed a common trend, with an increase in participation up to the 61-70 age group,

after which the number of participants declined. The study population of 90 patients was predominantly male (54 participants, or 65%), suggesting a male predominance in bladder cancer. The youngest age group (18-30 years) had only 8 participants, but numbers steadily increased in subsequent age groups, peaking at 41 participants in the 61-70 age group. This age group is frequently represented in health-related research due to higher health service utilization. Our study also reflected a gender disparity, with more males than females, particularly in the 41-50 and 51-60 age brackets, which aligns with studies indicating a higher prevalence of bladder cancer among men. A sharp decline in participants in the oldest group (71-80 years) may reflect challenges such as increased morbidity and reduced mobility that affect older individuals' study participation. These demographic patterns are significant for interpreting the study's findings, especially regarding health status and health-seeking behaviour.

In comparison to existing studies, such as Rohith et al. [8], which found a similar predominance of bladder cancer in elderly populations, our study supports the notion that bladder cancer is more common in older individuals. The majority of cases (62%) in Rohith et al.'s [8] study were between the ages of 51-70, with the highest incidence in the 61-70 age group. Additionally, our findings reflect a gender difference, with 87.9% of cases in males, which is consistent with the literature showing that bladder cancer is more prevalent in men, likely due to biological factors and risk exposures like smoking.

The study also assessed comorbidities, revealing hypertension as the most common, affecting 30.3% of participants, followed by diabetes in 26.5%. Other conditions, such as chronic kidney disease (CKD) and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), were less common. Notably, 26.5% of the cohort had no comorbid conditions. These findings are consistent with global trends, emphasizing the importance of addressing comorbidities like hypertension and diabetes in the management of bladder cancer. Our findings align with Puri et al.'s [9] study, where diabetes and hypertension were significant comorbidities, though we observed a higher prevalence of hypertension than diabetes in our cohort.

Tumor size distribution in our study showed that tumors between 2 and 3 cm were the most common (34.1%), followed by those in the 3 to 4 cm range (28%). Larger tumors (>4 cm) were rare, affecting only 7.6% of participants. These findings are comparable to those of Iyer et al., who observed that most tumors were small (0-2 cm), a group with a higher proportion of early-stage tumors. The correlation between smaller tumors and earlier stages emphasizes the need for early detection and intervention.

Regarding tumor grading, 60.6% were low-grade, while 39.4% were high-grade. Treatment efficacy analysis showed that Gemcitabine treatment resulted in lower recurrence rates at 6 months (15%) and 1 year (27%) compared to Mitomycin-C, which had recurrence rates of 23% at 6 months and 33% at 1 year. These results suggest that Gemcitabine might be more effective for preventing recurrence in the short to medium term, though Mitomycin-C remains a viable option.

Adverse effects were also evaluated, with urinary symptoms such as dysuria, urgency, and cystitis being more common in the Mitomycin-C group. Specifically, dysuria was seen in 7 patients treated with Gemcitabine and 10 patients treated with Mitomycin-C, while urinary urgency occurred in 6 Gemcitabine-treated patients and 8 Mitomycin-C-treated patients. Cystitis was more prevalent in the Mitomycin-C group (7 cases) than in the Gemcitabine group (5 cases). There were 43 adverse reactions, with 18 in the Gemcitabine group and 25 in the Mitomycin-C group. These findings suggest a higher risk of urinary adverse effects with Mitomycin-C, which must be considered when selecting a treatment.

Preoperative investigations revealed that most patients had normal blood parameters and renal function, with mean haemoglobin, white blood cell count, and platelet levels within normal ranges. Urinalysis results showed that Gemcitabine-treated patients had a slightly lower rate of abnormal findings (16.7%) than Mitomycin-C-treated patients

(21.7%), suggesting differential effects on renal and urinary function. Ultrasound findings showed that most patients had normal scans (68.2%), with bladder wall thickening and hydronephrosis in a smaller proportion (15.2% and 7.6%, respectively). These findings highlight the importance of thorough preoperative assessments in managing bladder cancer patients.

Cystoscopic examination revealed that 75.8% of patients showed no residual tumor post-treatment, confirming the effectiveness of the treatments. However, 24.2% exhibited residual tumors, suggesting that further interventions may be necessary. Postoperative complications were reported in 36.4% of cases, with urinary tract infections, bladder spasms, and severe dysuria being the most common. Treatment outcomes indicated that Gemcitabine had a higher complete response rate (50/66) than Mitomycin-C (45/66), suggesting that Gemcitabine may be more effective in achieving complete remission. However, Mitomycin-C remains an option for patients with partial responses.

Conclusion

Intravesical treatment with Mitomycin-C post-TURBT shows a potentially in reducing recurrence rates of bladder cancer compared to Gemcitabine, suggesting it as a more favourable treatment option in the early stages of bladder cancer. Further studies are needed to better understand the long-term outcomes and potential mechanisms behind these findings.

References

1. Cassell A, Yunusa B, Jalloh M, Mbodji MM, Diallo A, Ndoeye M, Diallo Y, Labou I, Niang L, Gueye SM. Non-Muscle Invasive Bladder Cancer: A Review of the Current Trend in Africa. *World J Oncol.* 2019 Jun;10(3):123-131. doi: 10.14740/wjon1210.
2. Grabe-Heyne K, Henne C, Mariappan P, Geiges G, Pöhlmann J, Pollock RF. Intermediate, and high-risk non-muscle-invasive bladder cancer: an overview of epidemiology, burden, and unmet needs. *Front Oncol.* 2023 Jun 2; 13:1170124. doi: 10.3389/fonc.2023.1170124.
3. Cockerill PA, Knoedler JJ, Frank I, Tarrell R, Karnes RJ. Intravesical Gemcitabine in combination with mitomycin C as salvage treatment in recurrent non-muscle-invasive bladder cancer. *BJU Int.* 2016 Mar;117(3):456-462. doi: 10.1111/bju.13088.
4. Alam SA, Morshed S, Uddin SMW, Saha PK, Rahman S, Begum SR. Intravesical gemcitabine and mitomycin C chemotherapy in the treatment of non-muscle invasive transitional cell carcinoma of the urinary bladder - a randomized clinical trial. *Bangladesh J Urol.* 2019;22(1):25-29.

5. Wang Z, Shi H, Xu Y, Fang Y, Song J, Jiang W, Xia D, Wu Z, Wang L. Intravesical therapy for upper urinary tract urothelial carcinoma: A comprehensive review. *Cancers*. 2023;15(20):5020. doi: 10.3390/cancers15205020.
6. Jones G, Cleves A, Wilt TJ, Mason M, Kynaston HG, Shelley M. Intravesical gemcitabine for non-muscle invasive bladder cancer. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*. 2012 Jan 18;1:CD009294. doi: 10.1002/14651858.CD009294.pub2. Update in: *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*. 2021 Jun 14;6:CD009294. doi: 10.1002/14651858.CD009294.pub3.
7. Zeng J, Funk J, Lee BR, Hsu CH, Messing EM, Chipollini J. Gemcitabine as first-line therapy for high-grade non-muscle invasive bladder cancer: Results from a tertiary center in the contemporary BCG-shortage era. *Transl Androl Urol*. 2023;12(6):960-966. doi: 10.21037/tau-22-772.
8. Rohith G, Gaur AS, Nayak P, Mandal S, Das MK, Kumaraswamy S, Tarigopula V, Tripathy S. Socio-economic, education, and insurance-related factors associated with the treatment completion rates in patients with nonmetastatic urinary bladder cancer: A retrospective cohort study. *Indian J Urol*. 2023 Jul-Sep;39(3):228-235. doi: 10.4103/iju.iju_116_23.
9. Puri S, Ashat M, Pandey A, Goel NK, Singh A, Kaushal V. Socio-demographic characteristics of cancer patients: Hospital-based cancer registry in a tertiary care hospital of India. *Indian J Cancer*. 2014 Jan-Mar;51(1):1-4. doi: 10.4103/0019-509X.134593.